

Towards Mapping and Defining Critical Hype Studies: Multidisciplinary Insights and Future Directions

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Abstract

Hype is no longer a peripheral element of technoscientific discourse; it is a central force shaping how futures are imagined, circulated, and enacted within innovation cultures. This position paper inaugurates Critical Hype Studies (CHS) as a collective, multidisciplinary field dedicated to unpacking the sociotechnical, affective, economic, and political dynamics of hype. Building on diverse disciplinary perspectives and empirical cases, we argue that hype is not mere exaggeration or distortion, but a structuring condition intertwined with funding, legitimacy, and power. Hype acts as a mobilizing, exclusionary, and performative phenomenon, shaping what futures are considered possible and fundable, often narrowing alternatives while amplifying dominant narratives. We offer a genealogy of hype, engaging with its historical, economic, and ideological roots, and survey adjacent theoretical frameworks, including the sociology of expectations, narratology, and other adjacent theories. Methodologically, CHS employs a broad spectrum from ethnography and discourse analysis to computational and artistic interventions, foregrounding reflexivity and cross-disciplinary openness. Key challenges – such as the “hype paradox,” harms and impacts, and discipline boundaries – are interrogated, alongside recommendations for future research, civic engagement, and educational

curricula to enhance “hype literacy.” Our paper maps CHS as a dynamic and reflexive endeavour, inviting broader scholarly and public participation to critically understand and shape the infrastructures and imaginaries through which hype circulates and endures. In doing so, the CHS programme aims to empower more equitable, plural, and sustainable technoscientific realities and imaginations.

1 Introduction

“Borin’ typin’, snorin’ pipe when hyper than four hypemen

Excited writin’, triflin’ times ten”

(MF DOOM, More Rhymin’, 2009)

“«Spene», diss’io, «è uno attender certo

de la gloria futura, il qual produce

grazia divina e precedente merto».”

(Dante, Paradise, 25¹)

Hype, once a peripheral concern in the study of science, technology, and society, has now become a central feature of how societal futures are imagined, circulated, and enacted. From academic abstracts to startup pitches, from policy roadmaps to media headlines, the language of promise, urgency, and transformation saturates contemporary technoscientific discourse. While hype is often dismissed as *mere* exaggeration or distortion, this paper proposes that it is something deeper: a structuring condition of innovation cultures, entangled with the infrastructures of funding, valuation, and legitimacy. Hype does not merely decorate science and technology; it helps produce them. We should normally begin with an etymological reference: where does the word “hype” come from? Nevertheless, controversy² in this area (as to whether the term signifies a shortening of the term “hyperbole” (Greek for exaggeration) or the drug-induced excitement after the use of “hypodermic needles,” only testifies

¹ “I said: ‘Hope is the certain expectation of future glory; it is the result of God’s grace and of merit we have earned.” (Barolini 2014)

² An interesting summary of this debate can be found in this online forum: <https://english.stackexchange.com/questions/253983/origin-of-hype>

the under-researched status of this area, while the word in itself has become part of everyday parlance.

This position paper marks an initial effort to formalize Critical Hype Studies (CHS) as an emerging field of inquiry. It draws on a wide range of disciplinary perspectives and empirical cases to argue for a shift in how hype is studied – not simply as a communicative excess or marketing tool, but as a complex sociotechnical phenomenon with material, affective, and political consequences. Hype shapes what futures are thinkable, fundable, and desirable, while simultaneously narrowing the space for alternative imaginaries. In this sense, CHS suggests hype is as much about exclusion and silencing as it is about amplification and spectacle.

CHS grounds in the premise that hype is not incidental to the innovation process but is constitutive of it. The challenge, then, is not to disavow hype entirely, but to analyse its mechanics, genealogies, and effects with critical precision. Who produces hype, under what conditions, and to what ends? How does hype mediate relations between science, capital, policy, and publics? What forms of power and inequality are sustained or disrupted through its circulation? And crucially, how can scholars, artists, policymakers, journalists, designers, activists and in general decision makers and professionals engage with hype without becoming complicit in its reproduction?

This paper is the outcome of a collaborative process involving 21 co-authors, each bringing distinct disciplinary insights to bear on these questions. Through shared conceptual frameworks, methodological propositions, and empirical case studies, it sets out to map the contours of CHS and articulate a set of principles and provocations for its development. In doing so, it invites a broader community of scholars and practitioners to join in the collective work of critically understanding – and responsibly navigating – the sociotechnical production of present and futures co-produced by the agencies of hype.

1.1 How This Paper Was Written

The genesis of this paper began with an initial conversation between the two leading authors concerning the emergence and urgency of CHS as a topic of scholarly interest. This discussion led to the convening of a double panel at 2024

at the joint meeting of the European Association for the Study of Science and Technology and the Society for Social Studies of Science (EASST/4S), where the aim was to develop a position paper that would synthesize contemporary insights and set directions for future research in CHS³.

Using existing networks and conducting desk-based research, a total of 36 scholars were identified and invited to contribute to the conference. Out of these, six submissions were received, some with multiple authors. The conference served as a catalyst for concentrating a critical mass of researchers further expanding the network. Subsequently, the final invitation to contribute as co-authors was extended to include some originally contacted scholars who could not attend, as well as new collaborators who attended the conference panel either as participants or through recommendations.

A structured set of questions was developed, aligning with the central themes of this paper: the scope and relevance of CHS today, its antecedents, theoretical frameworks, methodological approaches, illustrative use-cases, key obstacles, future directions, and recommended bibliography. This questionnaire was disseminated to a total of 37 scholars, and, with some dual authorships, this resulted in a collective of 19 co-authors. Notably, the two leaders of the paper chose not to fill in the survey to balance biases. During authorship, they had very little to add.

The leading authors embarked on drafting the initial manuscript, co-constructing it over a period of six months. Once the draft was completed, it was distributed to the co-authors for review, allowing them a month to approve, suggest changes, or update the content. The feedback received was meticulously incorporated over a year's period, culminating in the first manuscript that further benefitted from our network's gained experience and immersion into the field. Through this collaborative process, the paper represents a comprehensive and diverse perspective on the emerging field of CHS and stands as an example of the necessarily collectivist collaboration and exchange of information that we aspire CHS to be characterized by. This initial engagement with co-authors also formed the basis for an international initiative for the broader study of hype, now formally known the Hype Studies research network⁴.

³ <https://nomadit.co.uk/conference/easst-4s2024/p/14222>

⁴ <https://hypestudies.org/>

2 Background, Aims, and Relevance: Why Now?

In this section, we will aim to situate CHS in context by asking two key questions: what are the origins and background of hype that necessitate its critical study, and what are its current implications for the establishment of CHS field? The 2000s marked the rise, or mainstreamization, of emerging technologies such as nanotechnology, biotechnology, big data, internet of things, artificial intelligence (AI), and quantum computing, all of which have been particularly susceptible to hype. These technological advancements emerged against the backdrop of significant global shifts, including the deregulation of financial markets, neoliberal globalization, and the proliferation of the internet and social media as new media for circulation (Fijalkow 2013). It is no coincidence that a vast proportion of the literature on hype refers to it as “media-hype” (Vasterman 2005; Vasterman 2018; Elmelund-Præstekær and Wien 2008; Wien and Elmelund-Præstekær 2009) while, especially since the resurgence of AI hype in the early 2010s, “hype” tends to be chiefly associated with “technology hype.” In this paper, when we refer to hype, we mainly draw from lessons learned from such technology and media hype – with a particular focus on scientific communication –, however, we are further opening the agenda as to learn from other historical or domain-specific instantiations of hype.

We suggest that CHS offers a valuable lens for analyzing the mechanisms that drive future developments at the intersection of innovation, media, and politics. Hype aligns with both modern and late capitalist frameworks (Beckert 2016; Di Liberto 2022), since it thrives on creating and necessitating technological visions of progress. This dynamic is driven by opportunism and risk, projecting a reductionist, simplified, and unreflective future that often disregards social, political, and economic motivations and consequences. Hype does not only rely on promissory dynamics. It also frequently set normative agendas defined by “wishful worries,” a term coined by Brock (2019) to describe “problems that it would be nice to have, in contrast to the actual agonies of the present.” Utopian promises progress as interwoven with convenient dystopias, both distorting pressing concerns.

The relevance of CHS is underscored by two contemporary phenomena: the widespread presence of hype as a productive and pervasive force and the largely uncritical acceptance of both hype and actors: spin-doctors, tech gurus, followers, futurists, trend analysts, investors – among others, and further

extending to academic institutions (in both research and teaching domains, grant applications, curricula design), as well as the general public. CHS as a discipline, therefore, aims to achieve several goals:

Understanding Hype Production: It seeks to dissect the conditions, roles, and mechanisms that facilitate hype generation.

Reimagining Futures: It endeavors to cultivate societies less dominated by hype, where future aspirations are more aligned with achieving a attentive, thoughtful, sustainable and viable future amid multiple crises.

Problematizing Hype: There is significant potential to deepen our understanding of hype and problematize its conceptualizations. Traditional tools like Gartner's Hype Cycle tend to offer a simplistic (Steinert and Leifer 2010; Dedehayir and Steinert 2016; Alvial-Palavicino & Konrad 2016), standardized depiction of hype with a strategic focus on taking advantage of hype that is often generated by those who also present its curves (Pollock and Williams 2016).

Raising Awareness: It strives to elevate societal awareness, including among policymakers and citizens, about the risks associated with hype.

Exploring the performative agencies of hype: Understanding the relational properties of hype, and how it affects different actors in different situations will help acknowledging the diverse motivations and impacts involved in relation to sociotechnical and political implications.

2.1 Historical Emergence of Hype and Related Disciplines for Its Studies

Towards a Genealogy of Hype

An initial history of the notion of hype (Wadhvani and Lubinski 2025) explains how the term originated in the early-twentieth century to signal criminal subcultures (especially drug users and con artists), to then be revived in the mid-twentieth-century countercultures to distance themselves from mainstream culture. The contemporary meaning was crafted closer to the 21st century, around the emergence of a startup culture aiming at distinguishing itself from corporate culture by celebrating rule-breaking and embracing social

deviance as a marker of authenticity. This section will thus proceed by discussing: (1) historically hyped contents and examples (e.g., Tulips, gold rush), then (2) the emergence of performativity and expectations as theoretical frameworks, and (3) the broader historical and disciplinary contexts that have made hype, and its effects, especially relevant. However, a further history of the term is lacking, necessitating a look at adjacent fields and antecedents. While, in one sense, the feeling of hype treated as an affect or feeling can be viewed as ahistorical (expressions of exaggeration or excitement have dominated linguistic interactions for centuries), its manifestation as an effect is highly context-dependent. The shape, content, force, and speed of attention economies – evolving since the last century with the advancement of communication tools such as propaganda posters, street advertisements, and clickbait web design – produce historically constructed forms of hype grounded in a timeless human susceptibility to excitement. For example, historical cases such as Tulip Mania (1630s Holland), the US gold rush, and more recently, cryptocurrency booms, provide early and modern instances where hype – driven by both media circulation and economic speculation – shaped collective behavior and resource allocation. These cases illustrate how certain objects or ideas, by attracting high attention and investment, become focal points in historical economies of excitement and risk.

Indeed, a genealogy of hype reveals that it is far from a new phenomenon. Theoretical observations such as crowd behavior and the social contagion theory (Le Bon 1895), self-fulfilling prophecies (Merton 1948), moral panics and threats by conditions, things, or people (Cohen 1972), and the issue-attention cycle (akin to the later formulated hype-and-disillusionment cycle, Downs 1972) all attest that hype has previously been the subject of intellectual scrutiny, albeit prior to the establishment of the term, particularly within the technoscientific domain. The history of performativity in communication studies, and the sociology of expectations in science and technology studies, reveals how anticipation (Adams et al. 2009) – whether for technological, economic, or political change – shapes not only beliefs but concrete actions and investments.

Expanding Contexts: The Political-Economy and Ideology of Hype

In a sense, hype in the economic sphere comes to replace the formalized promises of the credit system to protect excitement in times of crisis – caused

precisely due to said excitement⁵ (on the technological hype as a form of contemporary informal capital, see Galanos 2025a). Under these lenses, hype should not be viewed solely as a phenomenon within technoscience; technology hype arises wherever there is significant popularity around an object or idea that claims to solve human problems or produce a desirable novelty. CHS should therefore aim to unpack and describe the historically contingent economies of attention underpinning hype and how these economies are sustained by political and sociological forces.

Hype as we know it today has strong ties to the business and technology communities, notably through technology consultants and inherently linked to financial interests and markets. Interestingly, there is a correlation between one's knowledge on a topic and their propensity to engage in hype, as noted by MacKenzie's certainty trough (1998). Those deeply entrenched in a (technological) subject are less likely to participate in hype (aware of an emerging technology's uncertainties). However, individuals with a superficial understanding, yet with sufficient vested financial or other interest, may perpetuate it with discursive certainty, and those with minimal understanding (greater uncertainty), yet, with interest from the user side, may participate in the belief of hype. Hype, moreover, is not solely a sensational exaggeration but is deeply rooted in cultural consciousness and modern science and technology's subconscious promises. For instance, singularity and transhumanism predict freedom from biological constraints through superintelligence, often removing political context from technological progression, drawing from vast cultural depositories of immortalization and life-after-death narratives. This often happens at the expense of neglecting parallel actions taking place simultaneously, as too much attention is drawn to the cultural promises and the trade-offs required to achieve them – trade-offs that are likely to become entrenched with lock-in effects once the hype fades. Hype is more than often related to sociotechnical imaginaries, which present what is yet to happen according to future-oriented optimism or pessimism (or a mix), often masquerading as factual rather than constructed (Castoriadis 1998; Jasanoff and Kim 2015).

⁵ Consider Karl Marx's account on the failure of the credit system: "in a period of crisis, the circulation of bills collapses completely; nobody can make use of a promise to pay since everyone will accept only cash payment" (Marx 1966: 540).

Critique and Decolonial Perspectives on Hype as a Tool of Power and Domination

This underscores the need to critically address the actors benefiting from these imaginaries and situating them within a longer socio-technical history. While hype is now becoming a term of everyday parlance, the various ways in which it operates have been described under various terminologies and in different contexts in the past. Breaking away from contemporary hype involves challenging the longstanding narrative of progress through technology, as underscored by decolonial frameworks that highlight how geopolitical power histories shape ongoing knowledge production and technological development (e.g., Escobar 2007; Mignolo 2007; Quijano 2000; Ricaurte 2019; Wynter 2003). Such an understanding equips CHS with a unification approach cutting not only across disciplines, but also across epochs – thus escaping hype’s fragmentary attention to the moment, to specific futures, and to particular domains without the broader social context.

Hypes are not exclusively linked to techno-financial capitalism but to the broader ideology of progress. Modern ideology, characterized by overstressing future potentials for opportunistic gains, can be observed in socialist, fascist, and capitalist societies throughout the 20th century. Such ideologies emphasize transformative aims through technology, war, racial purification, and so on, making bold claims about future trajectories and societal liberation via rhetorical and aesthetic means, from fascist radio propaganda to socialist realism (Marx, 1964, Edwards 1996, Nye 1996, Mosco 2005). Today, hype operates as an inherent feature of attention economy in concert with clickbait attention economy business models and strategies, fake news and disinformation, functioning both at a micro-level, from day-to-day decision-making and news consumption, but also on a macro-scale, dominated by the military-industrial complex and other sectors (academic, or even third sector) succumbing to national strategies that are influenced by, and influence, hype generation.

Understanding the politics of hype implies approaching it as a tool of power. From this perspective, the agents driving hype may have shifted over time, but vulnerable groups such as workers (whose employment status and working condition may depend on market rules dominated by hype tropes) or the environment (exposed to side effects of hype, such as excessive use of digital technologies with associated footprints) remain at risk, often seeing their rights and protections eroded under the narrative of imminent progress. Hype acts as

a dominance mechanism within scientific systems dominated by large corporations, prioritizing market-driven applied knowledge at the expense of fundamental research. This emphasis undermines the pursuit of broader knowledge and stifles non-mainstream research topics, cultural understandings, and the autonomy of scholars. Technology, rationality, and belief historically intertwine rather than oppose one another (Noble 1997; Stahl 1999; Davis 2004; Mosco 2005), warranting greater attention to the normative and performative aspects of hypes.

Critically examining hype necessitates positioning it at the science-media-policy nexus. The collaboration across fields like science and technology studies (STS), innovation studies, communication studies, media studies, cultural studies, social and political science, economics, critical internet, algorithm, data, and AI studies, history of science and technology, design research, and future studies can provide a comprehensive understanding. Hype can be linked to communication media reflecting modernity, from block-printing to radio and television, with early historical parallels in instances like the Tulip Mania in 1634–37, which illustrate modern hype phenomena driven by media circulation and risk investments (a historical assessment of fortune-making promises and losses can be found in Dennin 2019). Similarly, the US gold rush in the 19th century, involving large-scale industrial colonization of nature through resource extraction, the construction of railways and dams, early distributed “hype” as a signifier of quick fortune and societal progress, opening a trajectory of endless possibilities. The gold rush mindset exemplifies the interplay of economic promise, colonial mindset, media sensation, and public euphoria, offering plenty of fertile ground for novel case studies about present and historical events (Marx 1964) – for example, one may consider the proliferation of cryptocurrency mining and data extractivism/colonialism (Kumari et al. 2024, Howson 2020).

Hype, by strategically directing attention towards specific values, significantly influences the distribution of investment and global positioning, with powerful global players often having an advantage due to media access and globalization's reach. Such dynamics ask us to consider whom we prefer to champion for hyped leadership roles, currently often skewed towards middle-aged, wealthy elite, and mostly male and white figures, suggesting that most current hype is at the service of neo-colonial perpetuation (Sharma and Grant 2011, Heupel et al 2024, Wood et al 2024). Engaging disciplines like bioethics, marketing, and leadership studies may yield further insights into these hype

dynamics, while learning from histories of various domain-specific trends (such as from the music or film industry) can also be beneficial.

Historical Antecedents, Disciplinary Perspectives, and the Trajectory Towards CHS

So far, technology hype has been studied through multiple perspectives, however, these have never been strongly converging. Television presenter and journalist Benjamin Woolley's 1992 'Virtual Worlds: A Journey into Hype and Hyperreality' is a treatise (republished as a Penguin classic in 1993) on the hype around virtual reality with chapters on early Silicon Valley techno-euphoria hyping various elements of AI, the cyberspace, hypertext, and other forms of computing; Woolley analyses the emergent hype through the lens of Baudrillard's hyperreality. In 1995, astronomer and science communicator Clifford Stoll's 'Silicon Snake Oil: Second Thoughts on the Information Highway' claimed that excessive hype (1996: 13) obscures much required technological caution. In 2006, software designer Bob Seidensticker's 'Future hype: the myths of technology change' (2006) offered a critical perspective on the performativities of future imaginings upon present innovation. In 2024, after a one-and-a-half decade of continuous AI hype, computer scientists Narayanan and Kapoor's 'AI Snake Oil: What Artificial Intelligence Can Do, What It Can't, and How to Tell the Difference' (2024) stands as one of the many examples in which technical insiders aim to protect their own domains by potential harms caused by exaggerated claims⁶. The book 'After Hype: The Business of Taming the Digital Economy' by Pollock and Williams (2026) offers probably the first explicit call for a field of hype studies, building on, and extending, prior sociological frameworks such as the sociology of expectations and promise. Our CHS approach acknowledges these existing tendencies and aims at a strongly transdisciplinary approach to the field, one that places emphasis on the importance of multiple modes of expertise in the shaping and taming of expectations⁷.

⁶ Notable examples in the AI and robotics fields include roboticist Rodney Brooks's blog series (<https://rodneybrooks.com/blog/>) and the joint efforts of linguist Emily M. Bender and sociologist Alex Hanna's podcast series 'Mystery AI Hype Theater 3000' (<https://www.dair-institute.org/maiht3k/>).

⁷ Further building on the findings about the mutual shaping between exponential expectations and expanding expertise by Galanos (2023a) responsible for the production of hype, strategic hype assessment and sociological study should be sensitive to claims as much as actors.

2.2 Relevance for a CHS Field: Impact and Implications

The study of hype is essential to illuminate and challenge the strategies by which powerful entities manipulate hype cycles to concentrate power, undermine civic protections, and obscure the sociotechnical dynamics fuelling new products and services at the expense of the above harms. With nearly a decade of debating “fake news,” “alternative facts,” and “post-truths” (Farkas and Schou 2020) the role of critical hype studies cannot be understated. In order to articulate an active engagement with the phenomenon, this field must evolve beyond merely framing hype negatively and promoting a reactionary attitude to it, but to explore it as a performative agent, occasionally triggering innovation processes to escape “waiting games” (Bakker et al 2011). As stated above, there is a need to synthesize and build on existing literatures across multiple disciplines to tell more nuanced, multi-faceted stories.

CHS must foreground the power dynamics often overlooked in the relevant fields preceding its emergence, which tend to naively assume rational and inclusive visions naturally shape societal futures (Milojević 2002). Alternative future visions that are aligned with degrowth, climate justice, or economic redistribution often fail to live up to garner hype-level attention because they challenge the very logics they seek to dismantle: it is often hard to “hype,” to exaggerate and overpromise about something that goes against the very profit-driven and capitalist-reproducing motors of dominant hype. Utilising artistic and speculative methodologies can be vital to step “outside” such logical frameworks and constraints, for example, by practices such as combining techno-scientific critique with afrofuturist alternative imaginaries (Vidmar and Vermeylen, 2022) and through playful subversion of existing hype mechanisms.

CHS’s relevance lies in its ability to critically consolidate technoscientific and economic options that go beyond the linear narratives advanced by hype distributors and traditional future studies. The growing political successes of right-wing movements in the world, driven by fear and societal collapse narratives, underscore the need for positive, progressive, and emancipatory visions of the future. These dynamics encompass the contemporary process of financiarization (Krippner 2011) and assetization (Birch and Muniesa 2020), where speculative economies encompass increasing speculative technologies and cultures (Haiven 2014, Komporozos–Athanasidou 2022). Within this context, technology-focused hype often overshadows broader sociotechnical perspectives (Sloane, Danks, and Moss 2024). This calls for a scientific inquiry

field that critically examines technological solutionism, while promoting alternatives to capital-driven technology hype for various stakeholders, including students, communicators, policy makers and technology experts.

Viewed as a form of overstatement or exaggeration, hype is often only recognized in hindsight. Short-term impacts may be overestimated while long-term consequences are underestimated. This deep uncertainty about hype's potential consequences enables it to become an intrinsic part of the innovation process.

The centrality of social media in opinion shaping and group formation, alongside its emotional appeal, exacerbates the pitfalls of hype-driven technology promises. These dynamics carry significant implications for policymaking, as hypes can constrain the pool of viable solutions to contemporary challenges (Lee and Rid 2014). For example, an overemphasis on AI in decarbonization or adaptation discussions may limit the focus to high-risk, heavy infrastructure based, less locally relevant solutions controlled by a few. Another example can be found in the space industry, where we observe a convergence of entrepreneurial opportunism and the transference of public policy responsibility onto capital markets as done with NASA during the Obama government setting up Musk's SpaceX (Vidmar 2019), highlighting the urgency for CHS in these arenas. Such observations point to the potential for unexplored research into the intersection of policymaking and hype.

Power dynamics within hype cycles often affect seemingly powerful actors, such as policymakers and investors, leading to misinformed decisions that trickle down to less powerful groups or the environment. Addressing these implications requires a nuanced understanding of when, where, why, and how hype originates and how it interacts with media evolution and societal changes, ensuring that critical hype studies contribute meaningfully to both historical and contemporary discussions, that is, not only after the effect. Now that we have situated hype within a long and complex historical context and explicated its current embeddedness and importance for contemporary culture and economy, it is crucial to offer our working definitions of hype and CHS.

3 Defining Hype and Critical Hype Studies: Where Is Hype and Who Are the Hypers?

3.1 Defining Hype: Mission Impossible? Hype as Social Phenomenon and Performative Mobilizer

It is hard to define the slippery concept of hype. In this section we will focus on various approaches as the subject has been treated in the literature, or based on our co-authoring team's experiences, followed by our understandings of what can make the study of hype critical (in a dedicated section 3.2), so as to differ from mainstream apprehensions of hype as a market-oriented tool. To start with, technology hype is an inevitable part of the promissory work surrounding new and emerging technology. It involves exaggerated forms of discourse leveraging on contemporary need for novelty, stressing future benefits while overseeing negative consequences, simplifying the challenges to be faced implying labor, environment, technical feasibility and economic viability, among others. Often presented as a series of given facts or unavoidable futures, hype is propagated by powerful corporate partners in complicity with media outlets and powered by social media, generating uncritical reception among influential social groups.

As Alvial-Palavicino and Konrad (2016) and Gisler et al (2011) show, besides a form of exaggeration, hype is a form of increased media attention and a social phenomenon mobilising the necessary enthusiasm to stimulate actors to take risks and create and sustain protected spaces for new technologies. Especially in the context of public risk discourse associated with significant investment in emerging technology, mobilization of expectations has been seen as part of the practice of "risk-renormalization" (Vidmar, 2019). In this regard, the simplistic hype-cycle model operates both as an assessment tool while at the same time a folk theory used by technologists, consultants, policy makers and journalists alike. Labeling something as "hype" suggests an exaggerated status that demands attention. It indicates an initial surge of interest or confidence in a certain product or service, typically followed by a decline. The volatility that hype points out creates an urgent temporality articulated through the illusion of a rapidly closing window of opportunity that signals triggers of innovation for actors to cease playing waiting games (Bakker & Budde 2012; Bareis, Roßmann, and Bordignon 2023). This comes with an affective palette ranging from hope, excitement and fear, that however does not fade away with the decline of a

hype cycle. Hype becomes a resource that is constantly mobilized by a range of market players, alternative hypes continue to capitalize on the attention of various stakeholders, up to the extent that one may even understand hype itself as a type of less definite, or informal, credit/capital, something that is transactionally exchanged and contemporary systems of political economy (Galanos 2025a).

Hype as Intended Manufactured Practice

Indeed, hype reflects characteristics inherent in modern technological promises and the concealed intentions behind these advancements. Since it is a manufactured event both in the sense of strategic description of phenomena as “hyped” but also as instrumentally managed and tamed (Klingebiel 2022; Pollock and Williams 2026), hype stages and circulates a vision of the future that generates attention for opportunistic goals. It operates as a social practice that requires tools and methods, with specific actor groups choosing to engage in it based on how they define hype and their unit of analysis. Hype, therefore, dwells not only in textual communication but also in behaviors that inform others' actions, formal or informal. Drawing from business and management studies, as well as the theory of the Society of the Spectacle, CHS benefits from the knowledge that certain degrees of stage performance, strategic ignorance (or strategic ambiguity; Eisenberg 1984) or secrecy (Wark 2024: 260) are therefore a very likely definitional characteristic of hype, while entire word-specific strategies are now being deployed at the micro-linguistic, or micro-visual, level to attract specific types of promotional attention (Bordignon, Ermakova and Noel 2021).

Hype in Science Communication and Performative Expectation

Current scholarship, such as that by Millar et al. (2019), Millar et al. (2020), Intemann (2022) and Tsakalakis (2023), examines hype in science communication, noting its use of promotional language to embellish scientific research, thereby raising expectations that hinder intended communication aims, sometimes related to “empty signifiers” (Brown 2016), yet, sometimes inviting for the unification and alignment of scientific interests (Roberson 2020). Logue and Grimes (2022) define hype as a dynamic, collective vision that

mobilizes attention and action toward possible futures. It represents material-discursively produced hopes and expectations invested in technological or scientific objects (Selin 2007). Such hyped expectations performatively shape environments but are also often unsustainable in defining the trajectory of technological developments. Hype distinguishes itself as a normative phenomenon, taking advantage of various forms of rational thinking such as reductionist cause-effect relationships. It thrives on sensationalism and alarm, capitalizing on onto-epistemological uncertainty for opportunistic gains instead of broadening public understanding, literacy, or future possibilities. While some critics, like Powers (2012), emphasize the resulting “loss of value” in hypes as they distort what should actually be carefully looked at, we suggest that financial gains remain or are produced precisely because of hype as a tacit normative framework that acts as a redirection of economic, political or cultural profit (see also Taschner et al. 2021).

Who Are the Hypers?

Our authoring team frequently debated whether it is feasible or even desirable to establish a specific identity of “hypers” – those human actors responsible for the strategic generation, circulation, and exploitation of hype processes. If we, indeed, treat hype as a form of informal promissory note for capital gain, figures who benefit from hype circulation must be studied as part of a broader political economy of hype. “Here, politics is not considered something outside of us but part of ourselves. The life we invest in these figures is the same life that’s taken from us” (The Invisible Committee 2009: 87). “Hypers,” as we consider them, are not necessarily a fixed personality type but can be viewed as individuals or roles that exploit uncertainty about the future for opportunism. They craft overly optimistic (or often pessimistic) narratives which narrow imaginative possibilities in favor of their own interests (Bareis 2026; Pollock and Williams 2016; Galanos 2019), making hype a powerful political weapon, as the relation between AI and technoauthoritarianism shows (Bender and Hanna 2024; Belsunces 2025, 2026c). Such actors strategically exaggerate the value of forthcoming developments, often bypassing the need for nuanced or holistic understandings in favor of invoking emotional responses and perceptual sensationalism.

Out-of-Context Dynamics and the Social Life of Hype

The observation of strategic exaggeration aligns with Frankfurt's (2005) contrast of "bullshitters" and liars: like bullshitters, hypens are more committed to persuasive effect than to a careful or ethical engagement with the complex, multiperspectival realities of sociotechnical change. Spicer's "Playing the Bullshit Game" (2020) describes how "permissive uncertainty" allows speculative, unfounded claims to gain traction, as people respond more to the performance or salience of a speech act than to its descriptive accuracy (see also framing effects & speech acts). This creates a situation where hype – like bullshit – can be strategically exploited, regardless of whether its propagation is driven by ignorance or by bad intentions. A complicating factor, as Borup et al. (2006, p. 292) highlight in their discussion of technoscientists, is that individuals may shift between postures: projecting bold claims in public or entrepreneurial settings while exercising greater caution among expert peers. This further aligns with Eisenberg's aforementioned notion of "strategic ambiguity" (1984). These ambiguities raise questions about whether the focus should be on the psychology or the socialization of the individual "hyper," on the features of the speech act, or on broader sociotechnical conditions that enable hype. While such issues are important and the concept of "bullshit" remains both popular and contested, we believe a full psychogram or trait analysis of such "hypers" is beyond the scope of this programmatic article and merits separate, focused treatment elsewhere (potentially drawing from recent case studies such as Thiers, Martill, and Convery 2025, particularly as long as hypens are also public figures).

Nonetheless, exploring the conditions that make hype effective remains valuable. Echoing Milne (2020), one can see hype as a form of accidental or incidental fooling, wherein emotional and contextual effects may unintentionally mislead audiences. Hype's contextual (and sometimes "out-of-context"; consider Shi, Liu, and Srinivasan 2022: "We define hype news as information that is taken out of context, exaggerated, and overgeneralized to attract public attention") character is especially visible in viral pitches or media moments, where messages are separated from their information-rich origins and circulates in drastically simplified forms – heightening their persuasive force while detaching them from their actual context. This "out-of-context" dynamic escapes the confinements of media hype and highlights hype's complex social life, which deserves further scholarly scrutiny. The enduring complexity and partial

inscrutability of emerging technologies further sustain hype narratives, feeding into technomystical storytelling and the old adage that technical knowledge must, by nature, remain somewhat opaque to general audiences.

The Circulation and Complicity of Audiences

Circulation is pivotal for hype to function (Powers 2012). The audience, rather than passive consumers, become complicit collaborators facilitating hype's traction. In a sense, the audience may also play the role of "hypers," by complementing the process, although in a less intentional and strategized way. Media frenzy, led by social media and journalistic dissemination, amplifies the reach and influence of hype (epitomized in role of the "followers" in a situation akin to earlier anthropological investigations of popular frenzy⁸ in which moral panic about habit disruption allows the transgression of morals, until any remnant of the old habit is eliminated). Technological hype, as Stilgoe (2020) or Bourne (2024) suggest, involves acts of persuasion that mobilize communities through emotionally charged language and charismatic leadership. Hype, thus, validates technoscientific discourse that propels unrealistic expectations under socio-political, cultural, or financial incentives. Often the result of public relations and marketing actions, hype intersects with phenomena like disinformation, rhetoric, and agenda setting to design realms of the thinkable. Pretty much like workers without sufficient awareness that become complicit to potential labor exploitation in capitalist regimes, thus perpetuating the system, consumers "buying into the hype," are part of a similar hype-driven system that is based on the exploitation of sensations, futurism and presentism, for rapid financial and symbolic gain.

Future Promises and Expectations - Realist and Constructivist Approaches

⁸ "Ritual license [...] then assumes a character corresponding strictly to the catastrophe that has occurred [...] Popular frenzy is never resisted in the least way. In the Hawaiian islands, the populace, upon learning of the king's death, commits every act ordinarily regarded as criminal. It burns, pillages and kills, and the women are required to prostitute themselves publicly" while the frenzy "ends only with the complete elimination of the putrescent substance of the royal cadaver, when nothing more is left of the royal remains but a hard, sound, and incorruptible skeleton" (Caillois 1959: 115-6).

Statements involved in hype comprise of future-oriented or present-exaggerating promises that can spur excitement but may not withstand scrutiny post hoc. They frequently appear in the context of emerging technologies and political communications. The Actual Machine (AM) vs. Fucking Magic (FM) dichotomy in design⁹ illustrates the gap between technological reality and potential as framed by hype. It draws attention to enduring shared desires throughout history, while also showing how the FM aspect in technological perception may influence the coordination of efforts to achieve certain capabilities in the AM domain.

This resembles what van Lente refers to as the “realist” approach to the sociology of expectations, where scholars are called to determine the truth value of a given promise, as opposed to the “constructivist” approach to expectations that aims to assess the robustness of a given promise, but actively adding more perspectives on a given question by engaging stakeholders and collecting data (van Lente 2012: 776). We are interested in this double distinction (actual versus imagined capabilities and revelatory versus interventionalist approaches to promising) and we suggest that within the highly contextual environment of hype, all questions of this type are necessary.

To summarize, hype is pervasive across media, corporate events, high- or lower-impact journal articles, technical documents, marketing campaigns, political discourses and everyday life, driven by competitive research fields. It can be seen as a noise – sometimes benign, other times a distracting feature demanding too much attention, often associated with bad faith or ambiguity-aversion. As a process, hype is performative: it fosters waves of hope or horror, excitement or alarm, and expectations deriving from perceived promises like emerging technologies – or old technologies with new names. It serves an illusory yet productive role, distorting a technology's potential while enrolling actors around its promise. This duality invites further exploration into hype's nuanced impacts and manifestations across various domains, particularly through investigations of actors that we have identified as “hypers,” either strategic generators and distributors of hype, or consuming audiences who partake in the circulation and effectuation of hype.

⁹ A folk theory in design that we have, presently, been unable of locating its origin. <https://www.thoughtmerchants.com/quotes/am-fm-principal-actual-machines-vs-fucking-magic>

3.2 What Can Be Critical About Hype Studies?

In this section, we propose five elements that distinguish CHS from previous studies of hype. This is not intended to distance us from existing scholarship on hype, but rather to recognize and acknowledge it as the foundation of this academic project. We also recognize that, over the past two decades, these works have made significant efforts to describe and analyse hype—a task that is by no means simple. Our aim is to build on these laudable accounts and reflect on our own positionality in studying hype in all its elusive (hard to grasp), allusive (implies things), and illusive (creates illusions) nature and culture. These five elements are summarized as:

- (a) examination of power dynamics and contradictions of hype – including political, economic, cultural and ecological dimensions;
- (b) interrogation of multilevel and historical local–global dynamics of hype;
- (c) understanding of hype at the emotional and psychosocial level;
- (d) adoption of a normative stance and admittance about the researcher’s interference in the studies of hype;
- (e) and emphasis on the transgression or even abolition of “disciplines” as a barrier for understanding hype.

We suggest that these five elements have been widely lacking or in a nascent stage in previous examinations of hype.

The Politics and Contradictions of Hype

The critical dimension of hype studies that our paper advances examines how hype functions, who benefits from it, and how it affects various stakeholders. When conceptualizing the intent of CHS, it’s essential to explore who these studies are for and what they aim to achieve. Acknowledging the importance of “exposing” hype to the broad public, and the scrutiny of to which extent a specific hype cycle is true or not (this would be a task for the aforementioned “realist” approach, or more recently for fact-checkers). CHS, however, goes beyond the critique of hype to understand how it is produced and productive at the same time. For example, by understanding how those at the forefront of hype production – such as entrepreneurs, investors, and policymakers –

perceive and navigate it. CHS must consider the lived realities of engaging with and producing hype, showing how it is intricately tied to power dynamics akin to those described by Debord in his theorization of the “spectacle” (1988).

Hype plays a role in reinforcing privilege and authority, often due to who has access to speaking position, resources and the ability to trigger hype as a vast façade that simultaneously captures attention but alienates from processual forces at play. This double movement is also associated with perceptions of certainty and uncertainty. Previous research has shown that hype relies on strong rhetorical claims of certainty, while in fact thriving on injecting uncertainty rather than minimizing it. These claims are often binary and navigating in extremes (for example, the continuum AI utopianism–dystopianism), and deliberately vague, unresolved, and future-oriented. As a result, they generate attention through the speculative and evocative rather than the concrete and plausible (Nordmann 2007).

Evaluation of Hype with Emphasis on Dominant Narratives at Local and International Levels

Evaluative processes associated with hype, including its sociological aspects (e.g., Lamont & Swidler, 2014; Kjellberg et al., 2013), reveal that hype is not simply about hyping or buying into buzz, but involves various actors (and their associated “arenas”) navigating the dynamics in ways that make sense in their specific contexts. By examining who benefits from hype, who does not, and how, CHS highlights how these phenomena can overshadow alternative narratives and futures, ultimately narrowing the scope of potential societal developments. They also address how non-Western cultures might experience colonization through technoscientific hype, as such hype implies that technological progress is a universal societal goal, forcing other cultures to adopt these Western-centric values. This area is largely under-researched in any current or antecedent domain of hype studies, with few exceptions such as investigative journalist works (Arends and Kathryn 2025) on labor exploitation and AGI hype, or empirical studies on data colonization and crypto-colonialism, themselves not directly examining hype, but indirectly exposing its effects (Couldry and Mejias 2019; Herzfeld 2020).

Emotional and Multilevel Experiences of Hype

Beyond excitement and expectation, CHS should explore a broad spectrum of emotions like cynicism, disenchantment, alienation, escapism, and consciousness-raising. Research such as that by Kastenhofer and Vermeulen (2024) emphasizes broadening the emotional lens on hype. Understanding these emotions enriches the critique and highlights hype as an open-ended phenomenon – sometimes successful and sometimes failing – while placing the core of critical decision-making on the agents who are subject to, or responsible for, its circulation. This includes hyped practices in different scales, from research programs to governmental investments, from targeted advertising of new products to critical masses of populations entrenching the use of a new online platform.

Adoption of a Normative Stance and Co-development of Responsible Hype

CHS adopts a normative stance akin to other critical fields (critical data studies, critical race studies, tactical media, critical literary studies, and so on) examining structural inequalities that allow and result from exaggerations in technological discourse. Recognition of research's inherent political nature suggests being transparent about the values guiding CHS. While some scholars caution against trading scientific values for political activism, directing research questions to benefit certain political positions can help frame the discipline's goals towards broader, holistic, gains at the individual, societal, and environmental planes that consider intersections between species, social class, gender, race, ability, or age.

All such factors, isolated or in combination, invite for specific investigations within CHS, that in response to hype's velocity, call for immediate, and yet thoughtful, action and the associated disclosure of researchers' positionality to allow processes of reflexivity. It should be noted that not all co-authors of this paper adhere to identical or similar political principles; however, we are in agreement that hype, much like technology, has political properties, and our own political and social examinations of it necessarily interfere with our findings and interpretations. Within our CHS positionality spectrum, it is worth noting that some tend to follow an "over-critical" approach towards hype, sometimes self-describing their positions as "anti-hype" while others follow (and establish) what

is thought of as the responsible hype approach¹⁰. The former suggests that regardless of the content of the hype, its associated harms tend to outperform any positives; the later recognizes that hype is inherent to technological innovation and therefore it should be consciously displaced considering the values, and political and socioeconomic programmes it engages and reproduces. Collectively, we agree that both approaches have their merits and that given hype's highly contextual nature, they may both be equally valid strategies across different contexts.

Adoption of a Strongly Inter-, Cross-, Multi-, or Outer-disciplinary Mindset

So far, research on hype has been found mostly in the realms of STS, media and communication studies, and business or management and marketing studies. We aim to expand the reach of CHS to include psychology, psychoanalysis, politics, history, philosophy, phenomenology, statistics, economy, arts, design and other fields that may offer a more interdisciplinary and nuanced understanding of hype. Such lenses can help analyse how individual motivations, aesthetic trends and psychological processes interact with hype, addressing representation gaps across disciplines. A clearly defined research problem specific to hype studies could bridge discourse analysis, sociology, and other fields to focus on ephemerality and associated emotions. Analytical moves in critical hype studies involve retracing the conditions of hype, examining actor dynamics and events contributing to its emergence. Such genealogical approaches demonstrate hype's historical, economic, and political contingencies. Simultaneously, direct critique of hype emphasizes its visible negative impacts, with both approaches offering complementary insights (e.g., Markelius et al. 2024).

Our group has occasionally reflected on the nature of the very question "what constitutes a discipline," often finding ourselves restricted by disciplinary boundaries themselves but also at occasional odds with determining specific boundaries (what, exactly, is "transgressed" or "crossed" in many of the recent cross- or trans-disciplinary studies?). Further aware of the negative impacts (and indeed, the hype) surrounding terms such as "interdisciplinarity," we are

¹⁰ "Two great and apparently paradoxical merits: to exaggerate without exaggeration in a story; and to declaim without declamation in the tribune" (from a notebook written by Rémy de Gourmont, handed to Ezra Pound, as translated by the latter; Pound n.d.: 394).

often treating CHS as an “outer-disciplinary” endeavour that aims to maximize available expertise, theory, and methodology, regardless of its institutional label as long as it is relevant to the critical interrogation of hype, both in our attempt to situate precursors and antecedents or contemporary allies with aligned interests within the workings of the CHS programme.

4 Theories and Methods Appropriate to CHS

This section aims to demonstrate the various theories and methods CHS contributors have been employing in their relevant research or that have suggested could be relevant in the future course of CHS. We also offer a summary of existing use-cases, projects, or case studies that can act as early examples of CHS, as well as four group-based toolkits that our members have created to assess and map hype, foster hype literacy, and assist the de-entrenchment of hype. We acknowledge that, like in other critical fields, theoretical and methodological choices of frameworks are inextricably linked, or, indeed, sometimes designed as “theory-methods packages” (Silvast and Virtanen 2023) mirroring relevant scholarship on the inseparability between ontology and epistemology (Barad 2007; how we are as inseparable from how we learn), the conceptual and the empirical (Jensen 2014; our theorizations in constant flux with our observations, also mixing inductive and deductive means of knowing; Timmermans and Tavory 2012; Vidmar 2024). This renders CHS as a field that is constantly in the making, theoretically and methodologically, with the following list being only indicative of existing works that we are aware of, always open to additions as well as adaptations of our proposed tools.

4.1 Theoretical Frameworks

Hype is a multifaceted phenomenon and there are various theoretical frameworks that often may need to intersect in order to provide a comprehensive lens to study it. This collective study is primarily grounded in the tradition of STS, Cultural Studies, Media Studies, and Critical Future Studies.

A significant theoretical foundation is the sociology of expectations, explored in the works of Borup et al. (2006), Pollock & Williams (2016), Bakker et al. (2011),

Konrad et al. (2012). This framework provides essential theoretical tools for understanding the performativity of expectations, illuminating how future-oriented narratives influence present-day practices with particular focus on the crystallization of expectations from informal distribution of promises¹¹ to the “business” of consultancy companies and the establishment of policy that confirms on paper what was circulated as word of mouth, advertisement, or persuasive guess. The sociology of expectations further distinguishes between “arenas” of competing “enactors” of variant futures as well as the “selectors” (for example, policymakers) that solidify a certain suggestion by acting upon the possibility of a certain future, granting credibility to it. Further expansion into futuring practices, marked by recent studies on dramaturgical perspectives (Mangnus et al. 2021; Oomen, Hoffman, and Hajer 2022; Hajer and Pelzer 2018), provides insightful directions towards the “performative” aspect of hype. This approach allows for an examination of how specific actors stage envisaged futures in the present, moving beyond traditional present-oriented debates of structure and agency (Emirbayer and Mische 1998). These practices are critical for understanding the instrumentalization of hype technologies to influence expectations and actions, as illustrated by quantitative projections about AI's impact on global GDPs.

Narratology (Herman et al. 2010, Ryan 2016) is a crucial theoretical tool for CHS. The narrative aspect of hype is central, as storylines reduce discursive complexity, coordinating present activities and responses by creating a strong sense of urgency (Bareis, Roßmann, and Bordignon 2023). Lammar, Horst, and Müller (2025) highlight that these storylines often lack contextual specifics

¹¹ The description of Fama, Fame or Rumour in Virgil's Aeneid (29–19 BC), captures very well several of these aspects of hype, including the rapidity of information circulation, the added value of people pertaining into it, the way it creates “bubbles” (“puffs itself up”), the obscuring work it performs (the “cloud-base”), its constancy (the “sleepless eye”), and that it selectively exaggerates certain truthful aspects as much as it distorts others:
 “Rumour, the swiftest traveller of all the ills on earth,
 Thriving on movement, gathering strength as it goes; at the start
 A small and cowardly thing, it soon puffs itself up,
 And walking upon the ground, buries its head in the cloud-base. [...]
 A swift-footed creature, a winged angel of ruin,
 A terrible, grotesque monster, each feather upon whose body –
 Incredible though it sounds – has a sleepless eye beneath it,
 And for every eye she has also a tongue, a voice and a pricked ear. [...]
 Loud-speaker of truth, hoarder of mischievous falsehood, equally.” (Virgil 1952: 96–97).
 Virgil later masterfully creates a distinction between rumour (hype/misinformation) and credible, verified information:
 “This calamity came to the ears of Aeneas now, not as a rumour
 But through an official message...” (Virgil 1952: 304).

about the transition from current states to imagined futures, underscoring their significance in perpetuating hype. Such narratives necessitate fervent discourse through constant deployment of multiple media mechanisms and technologies of attention, overshadowing more nuanced or tentative modes of knowledge construction, generating an epistemology that is based on urgency and highly mediated immediacy. Actor–Network Theory, particularly Callon’s concepts of Enrolment and Mobilization (Callon 1986), elucidates how academic knowledge, commodified as an industrial product, influences technoscientific networks through hype. This acts, sometimes, as an opportunity for communities to mobilize towards a certain goal.

Complementing this is the concept of boundary–work (Gieryn 1983; Star 2010; Pereira 2019), which sensitizes researchers to how claims of scientific legitimacy are constructed and contested, a critical aspect in analysing hype through the rhetorical competition about preferred futures based on terminological shifts and negotiation of what is included or excluded from a sector or discipline as to credit or discredit proposed futures. Interestingly, hype is not only a matter of defending one’s boundaries – it may emerge precisely through the collision of contested futures, as it can be observed by the curiosity of experimentation with AI technologies that emerges out of constant salvatory and condemnation scenarios. Hype itself, thus, becomes a “boundary object” (Star 2010) that is not only strategically cultivated and concealed by the “hypers” but also attacked by “anti-hypers” (who, themselves, create “counter-hype” or “criti-hype” – a negative dimension of hype that surmounts as hype; Galanos 2019; Vinsel 2021). CHS can extend to the study of trends through a field theoretical perspective (Fligstein and McAdam 2015), for example in the case of music styles, shedding light on research dynamics and the saturation effects in visionary research. As certain fields become overcrowded and lose novelty, avant–gardists propel new scholarly trends – the digital sphere offers a constantly evolving terrain of and other linguistic elements focusing on different occasions on “information superhighways,” “virtual reality,” “web 2.0,” “industry 4.0,” “big data,” “AI,” “algorithms,” “quantum computers,” and more.

The exploration of hype extends then into wider social theories with emphasis on linguistic propagation as relating to human decision–making and action, including Situationism (Debord 1988), Post–structuralism (Barthes’s (1972) analysis of advertising “mythologies,” Baudrillard’s (1983) “simulacrum” of technological representations without referent, and Foucault’s (1972) discourse analysis), as well as Kuhn’s (2022) examination of shared (or disputed) lexicons

across scientific communities (this is, of course, a very limited list reflecting our authoring team's own biases and responses to the initial questionnaire; our network's collection of resources already offers a vast array of additional relevant theoretical lenses to explore hype¹²). These perspectives emphasize the distributed role of researchers, scientists, vendors, marketers, and audiences as simultaneous creators, maintainers, and recipients of hype narratives. These accounts unravel the complexity of how hype is generated and disseminated through less formal media and cultural channels as well as formal scientific reports and legal documents. Such social theories are further complemented by philosophical grounding in existentialism and phenomenology, drawing, for example, on Sartre (2020) and Merleau-Ponty (2013) to conceptualize hype both as contribution and response to existential ambiguity, as a human desire to concretely engage with ideas amid life's inherent uncertainty – and simultaneously create uncertainty through the over-production of new ideas. Merleau-Ponty's diagrammatization of Husserl's phenomenology of time (2013) is also useful in visualizing the role of multiple imagined futures casting shadows onto the present through the excessive energy of hype.

Overall, the theoretical lenses employed in CHS are diverse, rooted in STS, Cultural Studies, Media Studies, Critical Future Studies, post-structuralist social theory, phenomenology and narratology, according to suggestions made by the co-authors of this paper. This list is anything but definitive, but it is hoped that it can act as the point of departure for forthcoming studies on hype.

4.2 Methodologies and approaches

CHS employ a diverse array of methodologies and approaches to investigate the sociotechnical phenomenon of hype in its multiple contexts. While we hereby offer an overview of our contributors' suggested methodologies and approaches, we are further recommending that the expansion of methodological enquiry to different disciplines, such as neuroscientific studies of neural reactions to hype-inducing stimuli, paired to phenomenology-oriented interview- and ethnography-based descriptions may provide deeper insights into the lived experiences of actors involved in creating and sustaining hype. While the majority of our contributors happen to assume a qualitative approach to the analysis of epistemic constructions of hype and corresponding storylines, we

¹² <https://hypestudies.org/resources>

also suggest that quantitative computational analyses on hype may be necessary to count superlatives, hype words, and emotional terminology at a large scale (Wallenborn & Roßmann 2024).

Generally, CHS can be viewed as drawing intellectual legacy from the Constructive Technology Assessment (CTA) framework and method (Schot and Rip 1997). CTA, in its reflexive accounts of technological expectations and evaluation of the multiple technical, economic, legal, and environmental factors shaping technologies' empirical use as opposed to its intended or imagined one has always been conscious of hypes, even if not directly exploring them at least at a nominal level – nevertheless, it aligns well with other methodologies used in future studies. Currently, our approach draws from ethnographic and netnographic methods, such as interviews and multi-sited participant observation, critical discourse and frame analysis involving document and media analysis (Goffman 1974, Foucault 1972, Marcus 1995) that can help understand hype's transmission from journalistic to policy outlets and from science fiction to scientific publications.

Mapping variations in hype across different settings can help identify epistemological silos and ethical concerns. Analysing publicly available hype in various contexts – general media, industry-specific media, conference presentations, and pitch sessions – is crucial, as each medium represents a different facet of hype, demanding contextual analysis to unveil how hype is perpetrated and critiqued. Following the tradition of Technology Assessment and the learnings from research on Nanotechnological visions in the early 2000s (MacNaghten et al. 2005; Selin 2007; Grunwald 2010), Grunwald developed the approach of Hermeneutic Technology Assessment to better understand the dynamics of techno-visionary science communication and the impact of technofutures on the development of emerging technologies (Grunwald 2016). For TA and in the context of policymaking, this approach proved necessary, as visionary narratives about expectations and concerns came to dominate debates across the public sphere as well as within science, ethics, and policy. At the same time, anticipations of consequences grounded in even a modest degree of epistemic evidence remained unavailable. As a result, TA's established consequentialist framework lost its operational footing and, in specific cases, ceased to function altogether (Mehnert & Grunwald 2024: 281).

Holistic approaches to understand are manifold. For example, building on narrative hermeneutics by Ricœur (1984) and working in the tradition of Hermeneutic TA, the Futures Circle method (Mehnert 2024) critically

deconstructs hype by analyzing the societal meanings attributed to the technology through its visions. This method examines technofutures through three perspectives: prefiguration, configuration, and refiguration, exploring cultural presumptions, rhetorical devices, and impacts on discourse. Adjacently, Klingebiel (2022) offers a categorization of hype stages, from marketing claims to othering, providing a framework to understand the intensity and trajectory of hype from intentional device to its performative effects. These stages approach coincides with Michalec's (2025) findings through a multi-sited ethnography on hype about digital twins mobilising efforts, re-aligning actors after disappointment, concealing aspects of the process, and enabling reflection. Galanos (2023a, 2023b) offers longitudinal examinations of hype as a negotiation between arenas of legitimate expectations and credible expertise mutually influence each other further supported by wider popular science and science fiction narratives while hype shifts from domain to domain. Likewise, Belsunces (2025a, 2026a) explores the performative agencies of "sociotechnical fictions" to examine how the non-existent enters the existent through technosciences. In this regard, he investigates how such fictions – distinct from literary or cinematographic ones – operate at epistemic, aesthetic, affective, and normative levels. Last but not least, the Vision Assessment approach (Frey et al. 2022) examines how future-oriented visions of emerging technologies function as socio-epistemic practices that shape present innovation processes, knowledge production, and impact governance of emerging technologies. Rather than evaluating the technical feasibility of imagined futures, it analyses the meanings attributed to still-non-existent technologies and investigates how these visions circulate in political, scientific, and societal debates to coordinate actors, mobilise resources, and structure decision-making under conditions of uncertainty.

Such more general or traditional approaches can be strengthened by depth and investigative research "behind the scenes," aiming to understand psychological, affective, and sociological motivations for maintaining or generating hype as well as situating it within agenda-setting frameworks (Elmelund-Præstekær and Wien 2008), tacit or formal. This could be enriched by case studies incorporating a variety of data points, such as research programmes, grant statements (including unsuccessful ones), internal documents, think tank recommendations, social movement statements and interviews, that can provide a comprehensive examination of hype in specific domains. We would be as ambitious as recommending the interdisciplinary collaboration between social scientists and other members of the humanities with neurophysiologists to understand hype

processes at a simultaneously neuronc and social level¹³. CHS engages with the emotional dimensions of hype through the study of performative elements in communication, drawing from theatrical techniques (Goffman 1959, Oomen, Hoffman, and Hajer 2022).

These approaches underscore the performative aspects of hype as they are enacted and deconstructed through patterns, images, rhetorical devices, and the play of metaphors (for the latter, see Wyatt 2016). Likewise, longitudinal and historical perspectives contribute valuable insights into the evolution of hype over time, particularly in exploring the rise and fall of hyped objects, the replacement of attention from one object to another, but also the strategic rebranding of the same or similar objects to generate new hype through buzzword exchange (Rist 2007; Cornwall 2007; Bensaude Vincent 2014). A key reference in this regard is the comparison of several hype cycles that van Lente, Spitters and Peine (2013) conducted. Following on their work, this can be done in conjunction with aforementioned types of document analysis or simply close reading and systematic literature reviews that take time into consideration. Further empirical methods such as computationally supported visualization, influence of citation metrics (and other types of scientometrics, e.g. Bordignon 2020), trend analytics can be beneficial for mapping hype networks, revealing proactive research and corporate networks in various emerging areas (for an overview, see Bareis, Roßmann and Bordignon 2023: 13).

Both these methods – depth investigations and historical analysis – can help exploring the “ecologies of actors” (Hyysalo et al 2022), helping to dissect the dynamic interdependence of societal realms – or “social worlds” (Clarke and Star 2008). For hype to thrive and drive investment (or, indeed, for hype to act and thrive as investment), it must have an assumed innovation trigger, promises of profit, figures that present themselves as charismatic leaders and gurus, media amplification, political and industrial endorsement, and – very importantly – an accepting audience that can situate hype stimuli within contextual receptors. Hype is significantly drawing on the velocity of its circulation and the various speeds and rhythms by which it reaches audiences, or forecasts and influences events and actions. Therefore Lefebvre’s (2004) rhythmanalysis technique can act as a bridge between the personal and the social/historical aspects of hype, especially when the individual is confronted with multiplicities of – often contradictory – type of hype. Hype, in its complex existence as signal

¹³ Work akin to what is produced at the University of Edinburgh’s Neuropolitics Research Lab: <https://neuropolitics.sps.ed.ac.uk/>

(e.g. innovation trigger), symbol (a certain buzzword or brand), network (a connection of actors who are related around hype, even by opposing it), and institution (e.g. a research center justifying its launch and funding on the basis of existing hype) becomes that a very elusive element to study. Therefore, methods focusing on less rationalistic outcomes will be crucial in order to capture hype in its shapeshifting trajectories.

The integration of design, artistic and speculative research (Wilkie, Savransky and Rosengarten 2017) methods with social-scientific methods offer a novel way to engage critically with hype, exposing inconsistencies and challenges while enhancing communication with audiences. As most contributors agree, hype can be co-constructed also within the artistic realm, for example through science fiction depictions of existing or emerging technological futures, through participatory futuring (Belsunces et al. 2020) or through the introduction of new and hyped technologies within artistic creation (Belsunces 2026b). Employing art methods to explore and expose hype can be seen as an experimental approach to engage with wider audiences through techniques often associated with the expansion of hype, however, with a means to critique it. Further engaged research, exemplified by co-creative workshops with stakeholders, can assist investigating how individuals from multiple social groups respond to hype and its implications, employing media communication strategies to quantify message characteristics (Dewatripont and Tirole 2005).

We hope that this varied methodological collection provides a comprehensive (although open-ended) framework for understanding the complexities of hype, encapsulating its societal impact, communicative strategies, and emotive dimensions. The methodologies used in this study bridge STS, media, communication, and cultural studies with various intersections of qualitative and quantitative research, from historical and phenomenological to computational and neuroscientific analysis, to explore the performativity of imaginaries, focusing not only on dominant narratives but also on their manifestation in daily practices.

4.3 Use-cases

Existing use-cases in CHS offer a rich exploration of how hype manifests across various domains and its implications for technology, society, and communication. Several contributors highlight the power of hype within niche

sectors, each illustrating unique aspects of promissory narratives and their impacts. There is certainly some overlap between the following categories, particularly in the area of digital technologies such as AI or smart technologies, however we retained some tentative differentiation with respect to original terminological formulations. Since the initial conception of this paper and now, hype studies use cases have exponentially increased (as opposed to AI capability expectations) – hence the following examples can be treated as indicative. A rich array of different recent use-cases can be found at the Zenodo online archive of presentations held during the first Hype Studies conference, and the Hype Studies group’s participation at various conference panels¹⁴.

Quantum Physics Science Communication (Soto-Sanfiel et al. 2025): This study explores how quantum physicists perceive and use “hype” in science communication. Scientists admit to exaggerating their findings, mainly to secure funding and attention, but are concerned about the negative impacts on trust, research priorities, and reputation. While hype can spark interest and investment, it can also mislead the public, promote pseudoscience, and erode confidence in science. The findings highlight a tension between the pressures of competitive academia and the ethical responsibilities of accurate science communication, whilst recognizing how corporations gain from hype, letting quantum physics navigate a hollow gap.

Space (Vidmar 2019, Vidmar and Vermeulen 2022): Some studies focus on the space industry, particularly New Space entrepreneurship, examining how hypes around Martian and Lunar settlements present future visions that can transform societal issues and tackle climate change, or involve speculative futures of humans as an interstellar species. These narratives often overlook the technological and social challenges, echoing the historical evolution of space-related hype from religious and scientific discussions in the 19th century to the post-World War 2 military-industrial complex and modern space privatization efforts.

Responsible Innovation (Shanley 2022; Shanley et al. 2022): Another contributor investigates the emergence of Responsible Innovation (RI) as a movement, scrutinizing how hype cycles operate within this context. Despite objectives to transform scientific engagement, RI researchers often navigate normal science constraints and funding imperatives, inadvertently participating in the generation of their own hype. This highlights critical reflections on hype within RI

¹⁴ <https://zenodo.org/communities/hypestudies/records>

and contrasts with the necessary scepticism towards hype in emerging technologies such as genome editing, nanotechnologies, and AI.

AI and autonomous technologies (Bächle and Bareis 2025): The discourse surrounding intelligent machines is another focus area, where different contributors within an edited volume trace hype around machine creativity, anthropomorphism and autonomy, given in the civil or military domain. They examine the ‘vitalism’ scholarship that birthed ideas about autonomous, intelligent machines, revealing its connection between fact and fictions to the exploitation of hidden human labor in the Global South to render machine learning systems “creative.” This exploitation happens against a backdrop of hype narratives emphasizing the transformative potential of machine learning and AI.

Digital Twins, Models, and Infrastructures in the UK Energy Sector (Michalec 2025): This study examines how hype around digital twins in the UK energy sector first mobilized stakeholders by promising advanced real-time system models, then led to disappointment and a shift in focus toward underlying data sharing infrastructure. While initial enthusiasm spotlighted technical innovation, the hype ultimately concealed important governance issues – such as transparency of IT procurement, public engagement with grid changes, and sustainable funding – in calling for deeper attention to the political and ethical implications of digital infrastructure in energy transitions.

Artificial General Intelligence (AGI) Deep Hype (Belsunces 2025c): This work analyses AGI as a paradigmatic case of “deep hype,” a long-term overpromissory dynamic sustained by uncertainty and sociotechnical fictions. Despite lacking clear definition or feasibility, AGI attracts massive investment and political attention driven by venture capital. By identifying multiple uncertainty arenas – conceptual, application, temporal, value, governance, economic, existential, ethical –, the paper shows how AGI remains simultaneously imminent and undefined, operating as a mechanism of cyberlibertarian anticipatory governance.

Historical sociology of AI hype (Galanos 2019; 2023a; 2023b): Conducting a “historical sociology” of AI hype at the intersection between sociologies of expectation and expertise, this research treats hype as a longitudinal phenomenon that can be treated as a constant, with technological foci as variables, instead of a specific technology being the constant and hype/disillusionment about it being variables. This allows critical evaluation of

terminological choices to describe technologies in periods of disillusionment (for example, “knowledge-based expert system” during periods of “AI winters”), while it also suggests a definition of hype as the dialectical interaction between exponential expectations and expanding expertise: prestigious figures (with or without expertise on AI) can generate grandiose expectations (either positive or negative hype), while those who can generate such hype eventually become credited as experts.

Large Language Models (Dorofeeva unpublished work; Bareis 2026): Contextual examples include the terminological shifts in AI and internet technologies, particularly regarding machine learning and natural language processing (NLP). Increased hype around language models like OpenAI’s ChatGPT has elevated NLP’s status within the AI community, showcasing the influence of hype on shaping research priorities, networks, and academic curriculums.

Medical AI and Smart Technologies (Lammar, Horst and Müller 2025; Shen unpublished work): German AI hype is interrogated through media representation analysis, tracing how communication constructs AI’s epistemic referent and embeds it in hyped storylines. This research highlights varying perceptions and communicative practices across different contexts, tracing how communication constructs AI either as abstract and vague or as specific and contextualized. This research argues that rooting AI coverage in particular contexts and application settings does not inoculate against hype. Similarly, studies on China investigate the “smart technologies” hype, revealing the interplay between cybernetic theories and longstanding social concerns overshadowed by governmental and technological narratives.

Brain Preservation (Mehnert 2023): Examining the corporate hype created by Nectome, a company promising to preserve brains on computers, underscores how hype permeates mass and niche communication channels alike, illustrating its role in global narrative dissemination that is in turn based on age-old desires or fears that are mobilized in the generation of hype as convincing mechanism.

Quantum Computing (Mehnert 2025): Investigating the so-called bad actor narrative in contemporary quantum computing discourse, which frames potential technological harms primarily as the result of malicious misuse by external actors such as hackers or hostile states. The paper analyzes how this fearmongering hype-narrative is shaping policy agendas and investment priorities, legitimising technological countermeasures such as post-quantum

cryptography while deflecting attention from broader questions of power, inequality, and design responsibilities.

Datafication of Chronic Pain & E-Health (Charette 2025): This analysis explores the hype surrounding "e-health" innovations – like facial coding systems and virtual reality therapies – promoted as solutions to healthcare challenges. While advocates tout these technologies as paths to equity and efficiency, the study warns that privatization and profit motives can worsen access and amplify disparities, especially for marginalized groups historically subjected to surveillance or neglect. Qualitative research highlights that the real impact of e-health depends on social context, and that hype may obscure the complex realities of health, potentially reinforcing existing injustices rather than resolving them.

Synthetic Data (Ravn 2025): An investigation of the growing interest in synthetic data, focusing on how its promises are constructed and disseminated. This study draws on empirical sources like scientific literatures, reports, webinars, and interviews. It identifies key shifts in perception: synthetic data has moved from a vernacular term to a scientific concept, transitioned from a possibility to an inevitability, and evolving from a research technique to a societal promise. Moreover, this work highlights three types of boundary-work: claims of epistemic superiority, discussions on appropriate methodologies, and debates about whether synthetic data are "fake".

Architecture (Blackwell 2023): The study of new laboratory facilities, linked to the isolation of graphene, exemplifies graphene hype perform material agencies in the build environment by stimulating the construction of new buildings, while at the same time it shows how architectural design and infrastructure contribute to hype as a mobilizing factor rather than a negative one. Studies of hype in architecture show how talent attraction and concentration through hype within facilities designed by "starchitects" showcase their performative potential in stimulating innovation by generating hype that can bring together humans with great ideas.

Graphene (Alvial-Palavicino & Konrad 2016): More specifically on the graphene hype, other contributions explore how technology consultants navigate and operationalize the notion of hype in the context of graphene and 3D printing. The analysis identifies that hype is assessed through technical expertise, as a collective social dynamic, and within situated interactions. These modes of engagement offer consultants flexible repertoires to interpret and stabilize

expectations, while simultaneously positioning themselves as indispensable intermediaries. These cases illustrate how, rather than demystifying hype, consultants participate in its circulation and modulation, thereby contributing to the shaping of emerging innovation landscapes.

Further, the wide-ranging hype phenomenon is documented through case studies on how hype contributes to the neglect of orphan disease research funding (Tsakalakis 2025), and the questionable efficacy of celebrity activism in addressing global issues like climate change and world hunger (Tsakalakis 2021; Tsakalakis 2023).

Together, these examples illustrate the richness of CHS as a field, demonstrating a vast array of areas that can be explored through this lens and its relevance to virtually every technoscientific domain given that none can be immune to hype-related phenomena.

4.4 Tools for Hype Assessment, Hype Literacy, and Hype De-entrenchment

Members from our authoring team and associated network have designed tools to understand the social and historical construction of hype processes, assess its impacts, and promote literacy about it.

One tool is the Hype Studies Workshop assessment tool (Galanos 2025b). This workshop is designed to last for approximately one to two hours and is directed to scholars with interest in science and technology, policymakers, professionals, technologists (e.g. IT specialists), and any other members of the public interested in these areas. During a post-it style session, participants are invited to answer the following questions, informed by actor-centric models of assessment, narrative analysis, and the sociology of expectations: “What are the dominant narratives driving the hype? Who are the key actors promoting these narratives and why? What promises are being made about the technology's potential? When did hype first manifest in that area?” Participants there are invited to discuss further: “who is promoting the hype (e.g., companies, media, researchers) and their reasons (e.g., funding, visibility, market advantage), “who is partaking into hype, who, how, and why believes in it – and how hype gains legitimacy,” and create a visual map of their findings. Lastly, participants aim to analyse hype on the basis of the following questions: “how does hype influence

funding and policy decisions? What are the potential risks and benefits of the hype? What does hype obscure (e.g., moral concerns, technical limitations, alternative solutions, labor, material/environmental processes)? Are there intended or unintended positive outcomes or side-effects of hype?." The workshop can thus readily lead to the production of a quick brainstorm around a given technology with adjustable degrees of contextualization for different sectors, organizations, or scholarly research.

The Hype Literacy Toolkit (Belsunces 2025b) is conceived as a practical resource to explore how hype participates in the collective governance of emerging technologies. Using a card deck that presents a series of hype triggers such as future visions, emotional rushes, expert halo effects, urgency modes, and false certainty, participants analyse a specific form of technological hype. By distinguishing between alarmism and optimism – two forces mobilized in hyping or counter hyping – and working through a worksheet, groups of up to five participants explore how different actors such as journalists, technologists, investors, researchers, policymakers, activists, and citizens engage with hype. Specifically, participants examine how these actors are affected by hype, who benefits from it, and who is harmed, included, or excluded. Through guided exercises and scenario based discussions, participants examine how hype frames expectations, channels attention, and steers decision making under conditions of uncertainty. The toolkit can be used by any number of participants, provided there are sufficient cards and worksheets. To ensure meaningful discussion within each group and collectively, the workshop should last at least two hours.

The Oblique Manoeuvres card deck (Michalec et al. 2025) offers an gamified approach for innovators and R&D teams seeking to break through creative impasses, particularly those compounded by hype and high expectations. Adapted from Brian Eno's classic *Oblique Strategies*, this edition contextualizes prompts for the complex pressures and uncertainties of contemporary innovation environments – drawing directly on empirical research with energy sector entrepreneurs and technologists. During solo or group sessions, participants identify current challenges or decision points within their projects and draw cards containing abstract or provocative prompts. Rather than direct solutions, these "manoeuvres" invite users to consider alternative perspectives, "prototype the absurd," or interpret advice from the vantage point of stakeholders such as users, investors, or managers. Sessions can be structured with facilitators, timers, or reflective notetaking, and are flexible enough to

support brainstorming, collaborative debate, and critical analysis of entrenched assumptions – including hype-induced biases. By deliberately destabilising linear or habitual thought processes, *Oblique Manoeuvres* helps teams move beyond surface narratives, critically assess the role of hype (and anti-hype) in their work, and foster both individual and collective literacy in creative, reflective problem-solving. Like the Hype Assessment and Literacy Toolkit, the card deck can be readily incorporated into workshops or daily practice and is available for adaptation under a Creative Commons license, amplifying its utility as both a practical tool and a pedagogical resource for innovation communities.

The *Critical Cartography of Hype* (Oberson 2025) workshop, inspired by the collective mapping practices of the Argentinian *Iconoclastas* and the German *kollektiv orangotango*, offers a participatory method to analyse hype as a sociotechnical and political phenomenon. Drawing on traditions that understand maps as instruments of power, the workshop reclaims cartography as a critical and emancipatory practice capable of revealing how hype circulates across disciplines, mediates power relations, and shapes technological imaginaries. Through hands on, pen and paper collective mapping, participants contribute concepts, visuals, and experiences from their own fields, collaboratively constructing a shared cartography that connects historical, political, social, and cultural dimensions of hype. This process functions simultaneously as critical inquiry, open-ended archive, and analytical infrastructure, fostering reflexivity and collective awareness while exposing asymmetries, invisibilities, and mechanisms of influence. Guiding questions explore whether hype has a territory, ecology, or specific power structures, and how it shapes governance, media, and technological futures. The resulting map is conceived as an evolving, open resource, later translated into an accessible online platform that remains editable and expandable. By externalising distributed knowledge and connecting theory with situated experience, the workshop strengthens collective literacy around hype and contributes to the development of shared analytical tools for the emerging field of CHS.

5 Challenges in CHS, Future Directions, and Teaching Agenda

Why is it so difficult to study hype? Because its meaning is so fluid, because as soon as a hype object is identified it transforms to, or is replaced by, another, because those who generate hype strategically make many efforts to conceal the intentional production of hype, also blocking the access to the gates leading into hype formation processes, and because it is extremely hard to avoid becoming part of the growing hype economy while studying it. So far, this position paper explored past and present literature, theories, methods, and use-cases associated with CHS. In this section, we offer challenges that the proposed field has faced or may be faced with in the future. This enables us to recommend a list of potential directions for future research and activities, including a teaching agenda about hype that, as noted by multiple co-authors, is lacking from current teaching curricula.

5.1 Key Obstacles in CHS

CHS faces numerous obstacles that challenge their development and effectiveness in analyzing and critiquing hype in technology and science. Some of them will be directly relatable to numerous social scientists and may seem like reiterations of well-known problems contextualized in the realm of hype as a studying phenomenon; however, some relate directly point to hype's uniqueness as a complex and elusive, highly context-dependent field, characterized by extreme visibility in its manifestation and extreme secrecy in its generation.

Intended or Unintended Hype

One primary difficulty lies in distinguishing between hype as a deliberate, calculated device and the sincere beliefs of its proponents regarding transformative technologies. Such an analysis requires extensive ethnographic data collection, making it difficult to discern deeper motivations behind public displays. In turn, gaining access to empirical data for discourse or network analysis poses significant frustrations, especially as communication becomes

increasingly restricted on privatized platforms like social media. The challenge is exacerbated when attempting to engage with participants in hype-related decision-making processes and how tools like the Gartner Hype Cycle may assist these processes.

The Hype Paradox

A notable meta-cognitive challenge in CHS is what some of us refer to as the “hype researcher’s paradox.” This paradox raises the question: Do researchers studying hype risk inadvertently contributing to the very phenomenon they seek to critique? Cf. Russell’s paradox in set theory: “The class of all sets which are not members of themselves is not a set” (Mycielsi 2004) – to paraphrase, the set of all researchers who do not contribute to hype may itself contribute to hype by studying it; researchers who distance themselves from hype risk becoming part of the hype process by drawing attention to its negative form, hype about anti-hype. By drawing further attention to hype – whether through academic scrutiny, media engagement, or public discourse – CHS scholars may help stabilize, reproduce, or redirect hype, reinforcing its prominence. This recursive dynamic means that critical attention itself risks amplifying the salience of certain hype narratives, whether by reinforcing popular tropes or by shifting the attention toward competing issues (for example, moving the spotlight from apocalyptic AI discourse to more immediate concerns like technological deskilling).

This dynamic raises a dilemma: On the one hand, if CHS scholars strive to avoid any role in reproducing hype, they may inadvertently marginalize their own field, making it less visible or less compelling, and potentially failing to attract the recognition, support, and funding necessary for its further development. On the other hand, if they engage robustly enough to establish CHS as a credible and recognized field, there is a risk that the mechanisms of attention-seeking (via conferences, grant proposals, or public engagement) will mimic or feed into the very cycles of hype they hope to analyze and critique. This dilemma extends the well-known one of scientific hype, where scientists navigate the necessity to hype their field while at the same time maintaining distance from sensationalism (Rinaldi 2012).

Clarifying the “hype paradox” as we mean it, then, is less about logical contradiction and more about a practical, normative challenge: the very act of

repetition, amplification, or even critical scrutiny can reinforce the salience of hype. Thus, the “stage” (venue, channel, audience) and the style of engagement matter fundamentally for determining whether such activity is appropriate or inadvertently self-defeating. This challenge is evident, for example, in the necessity of funding applications, promotional activities, and strategic positioning within competitive academic, media, and policy environments – practices that often rely upon forms of hype or at least capitalizing on its dynamics.

Some counterpoints can be raised: scholars in CHS may in fact face significant obstacles due to the continued marginalization of “hype” as a niche or under-recognized topic in communication, STS, or policy research. This situation limits the confidence, resources, and interdisciplinary collaboration available for CHS research in the first place. Thus, the risk of “overhype” or exploiting academic attention is perhaps less pressing than the struggle to legitimize critical research on hype at all. Nonetheless, any efforts to remedy marginalization must remain reflexive, as moves to secure support for CHS may themselves be drawn into cycles of competitive self-promotion.

Rather than looking for an easy resolution, CHS might draw from practices of critical reflexivity in other fields: maintaining awareness of the political, epistemic, and performative stakes entailed in how hype is addressed, and keeping the field honest about its own risks of entanglement. A sober engagement means not only critiquing hype, but being attentive to the venues, practices, and effects of one’s own interventions – avoiding either reckless participation in hype cycles, or an apologetic stance that paralyzes the field. Ultimately, while scholars cannot hope to “prevent” hype altogether, they can work to navigate its challenges conscientiously, focusing on transparency and methodological rigor about their own positionality within economies of attention and novelty – or even, following the aforementioned Situationist path, “hijacking” the methods of hype through subversion, using its means against itself.

Constitution of Hype Harms

Another challenge is the identification of what constitutes hype-driven harms and the mobilization of more relevant alternatives to address technology and science-related sociopolitical problems. Hype often outlines both diagnostic and solution framing, thus complicating the process of critiquing and addressing

these issues due to its pervasive influence and lack of clarity in its demarcations. Hype is offering a linguistic set to play with that one has to assimilate and understand in order to critique but also be able to counteract through alternative linguistic sets that go beyond the mere correction of terms. This can be called the syndrome of false diagnosis: “you say the problem is AI, but it’s data;” “you say the problem is race, but it is gender” – instead, entire new languages have to be counter-proposed to break with the rules of the hype game. That is, focusing on the early causes of hype-driven harms instead of its myriad manifestations, or challenging the prominent speaking position of opportunistic hype agents in media – instead of criticising their claims, which can just result in more attention traffic. This challenge directly relates to the previous one as, the more one becomes immersed in the study of hyped objects, the harder it is to abstain from hyped languages. This, finally, extends to the very definition of “hype” and it becomes an essential task for CHS to clearly study assumed differentiations between related concepts such as hype, trend, sensationalism, and alarmism, which remain underexplored conceptually.

The critical role of thinkers in promoting academic, scientific, activist, and artistic work that respects environmental, nonhuman, and human values is essential. However, the dominance of neoliberal practices and competition undermines deep thinking, solidarity, and intellectual diversity. Hype in science communication reflects this dominance, prioritizing specific topics and corporate interests over societal (or sociotechnical) questions, which hampers long-term diverse thought and cooperation. Once again: how much can subversive usages of hype tactics within a neoliberal system remain protected from cooptation, ensuring a positive, progressive and transformative change from within, rather than being absorbed by the target and transformed into one of its tools for dominating critical thinking? Identifying who benefits from the funding of such studies by demonstrating how understanding hype dynamics contributes to broader research and practical outcomes can be revelatory about understanding hype mechanisms themselves.

More practically, science communication researchers, often from sociology or STS, may disregard micro-level approaches that explore audience research in detail. The movement between general and specific contexts of hype presents challenges in forming cohesive claims about its production. This includes acknowledging diverse geographies and histories of hype and tying together disparate types of micro and macro-sociological lenses.

These challenges are unlikely to be resolved any time soon. Yet, we suggest that their acknowledgment and constant awareness about their potential impacts will be key in every reflexive practice, while it is our hope that members of the CHS community will be constantly on the lookout offering critique on CHS blank spots based on the above.

5.2 Future Directions

As CHS evolves, several future directions and open questions could shape its development. A primary consideration is whether the field aims to synthesize existing literature, cross-pollinate across disciplines, or propose new concepts and research methods for examining hype. Determining the target audience for this research – whether academia, industry, policymakers, or the general public – is also crucial. In our view, CHS is relevant to every audience, while every audience can inform CHS, as hype seems to leave no aspect of the planet (and even outer space; Tutton 2018) unaffected in more or less direct ways. At the same time understanding the role of expertise in the shaping of hype is crucial: who is entitled, and under what credentials and circumstances, to shape and legitimize hype; and at the same time, how does hype itself shape our judgement precisely about the demarcation of such relevant expertise?

A significant future direction involves examining the role of CHS as a meta-analysis of hype itself, also based on the previously mentioned “hype paradox.” To establish CHS, researchers may need to participate in the very cycle of hype they aim to critique, by garnering support, securing resources, and building research networks. This paradox invites an engaging avenue for empirical research; for instance, an auto-ethnographic study could explore the types of hype necessary to establish a new field of study and reflect on the experiences of CHS proponents in navigating this landscape.

Additionally, the way hype is perceived in media and industry spaces has shifted in the last decade. The term “hypey” is now commonly used as a conversation starter, particularly in discussions about technology like AI. Researchers should explore the implications of this shift, including how acknowledging hype upfront might shield discussions from further critique, potentially sidelining the issue through a “chilling effect” that treats this as “mere” humor, rather than addressing it substantively. Investigating a more “hype-aware” world, wherein individuals and organizations navigate discourses that could derail their

progress, could yield significant insights into current communication strategies within the technology and science ecosystems.

Moreover, CHS could explore how hype functions within technoscientific networks to advance political projects, as described by Hessenbruch (2004). Particularly, the focus could be on how hype brings certain technologies with perceived social and environmental benefits to the foreground of public discourse while potentially concealing those with more destructive implications. Understanding this dynamic could enable CHS to better influence public discourse and policy, ensuring that beneficial technologies receive appropriate attention while more harmful ones are scrutinized and regulated effectively.

In this regard, the Hype Studies group convened a double panel at the European Technology Assessment Conference 2025 to explore the need for hype assessment¹⁵. This emerging subfield within CHS aims to raise awareness among industry and policy stakeholders about how hype nudges, misdirects, or (un)intentionally stirs decision-making processes. Along these lines, the group is editing a series on hype, politics and technology at Tech Policy Press¹⁶, featuring original articles by international experts. The series is translated into Spanish, Catalan, Portuguese, German, and Polish.

This brings us to a practical recommendation for the formation of a critical hype observatory¹⁷ – a civic tool for the reporting of hype and collection of instances of hype across various documents that could be open to any interested party to contribute but also use for research. Hype is, if anything else, a social and political endeavour that, like technology, is constructed through multiple intersections of intentional and unintentional biases and agendas. Civic participation in CHS may be crucial for opening up the debate about hype to wider audiences that are all subject to, and responsible for, hype generation, maintenance, distribution, and abandonment.

By addressing these future directions, CHS scholars can contribute to a more reflective and informed understanding of hype, enhancing critical engagement across diverse sectors. These recommendations are only indicative and it is our

¹⁵ <https://www.oeaw.ac.at/en/ita/etac6/etac6-programme-day-3>

¹⁶ <https://www.techpolicy.press/category/the-hype-studies-series/>

¹⁷ On the 15th of December 2025 the MIT Technology Review launched a special editorial package entitled “Hype Correction” intended to “reset expectations” after years of AI overpromising. The Critical Hype Observatory should follow the same objective, but applied to a wider range of topics, and with a more open, participative and pedagogic approach.

hope that CHS will be enriched by the growing number of hype scholarship asking new questions and offering new directions to CHS.

5.3 Teaching agenda

A critical examination of hype is noticeably absent from most current educational curricula, despite its pervasive influence on technological, scientific, and societal narratives. As such, developing a comprehensive teaching agenda for CHS is essential to equip students of various levels with the tools to understand, critique, and influence the discourse surrounding emerging technologies, even through training on the creation of hype narratives.

The teaching agenda for CHS can draw on interdisciplinary approaches, integrating insights from ecologist, feminist or black STS and literary analyses of science fiction narratives. This fusion (with an early example in Mangnus et al. 2021), enhances students' "future literacy" (Miller 2015) by drawing on the aforementioned criteria for a *critical* hype studies, encouraging them to explore how hype shapes and distorts our understanding of potential futures, how it marginalizes certain communities or reproduces power imbalances, and how it travels through relatively innocuous networks, establishing itself simultaneously on multiple registers of the social.

A key component of the CHS teaching strategy involves project-based exercises where students critically analyze the staging of digital futures. Through these exercises, students can be tasked with modulating specific dimensions of these futures that point towards utopian and dystopian narratives. This creative engagement allows students to actively unpack and reimagine powerful tropes, understand the use of metaphors or broader rhetorical strategies, and unspoken assumptions that underpin much of the technological hype, fostering critical thinking and reflexivity.

This pedagogical approach not only nurtures students' analytical abilities but also empowers them to question and reframe dominant narratives. By simulating real-world scenarios and encouraging explorative learning, students become adept at identifying and challenging the mechanisms through which hype is generated and sustained. Such CHS-inspired courses can be thought of as equivalents or historical extensions of courses on critical thinking or critical media/information/data/AI literacy.

6 Conclusions

This paper has sought to chart the emergence and stakes of CHS as a vital field for interrogating the pervasive and often underexamined phenomenon of hype. Drawing on a wealth of interdisciplinary scholarship, collective reflection, and situated case studies, we have argued that hype is not a peripheral or ephemeral feature of technoscientific life, but a constitutive element of contemporary innovation cultures – shaping what futures become possible, permissible, and profitable. By exploring hype’s affective power, material consequences, and underlying politics, CHS provides much-needed analytic tools, both theoretical and methodological, to disentangle how market logics, media dynamics, and sociotechnical imaginaries mutually reinforce exclusionary visions and practices.

We have surveyed the varied genealogies, definitional challenges, theoretical lenses, and methodological innovations that comprise the emerging ecosystem of CHS. In doing so, we have highlighted the necessity of reflexivity, cross-disciplinary openness, and attention to multi-scalar power relations in any robust analysis of hype. Our collective reflection underscores the paradoxical position of CHS scholars, who must critically hold hype at arm’s length while also navigating the seductive gravitational forces of visibility and relevance within the very systems they critique. We are aware of our own CHS writings potentially generating hype themselves, since hype, as a psychological phenomenon, occurs unexpectedly, depending on a subject’s openness to receiving it. Therefore we, with various degrees among the authors, do not condemn hype as a whole, but we alert towards its importance when it comes to power imbalances.

The future of CHS depends on embracing this paradox – not as a paralyzing double bind, but as a productive space for critical inquiry and intervention. To this end, we propose sustained collaboration between academic researchers, practitioners, journalists, artists, designers, policymakers, and civil society actors. Vitality, we advocate for educational and civic practices that foster “hype literacy,” enabling emerging generations not only to navigate and critique hype, but to reimagine and redirect it towards more pluralistic, equitable, and sustainable futures.

The path forward for CHS is necessarily collective, experimental, and adaptive. We encourage scholars and practitioners from diverse domains to contribute to

this evolving field: to question whose interests current hypes serve, to amplify alternative narratives, and to interrogate the infrastructures through which hype circulates, hides, and endures. Only through such ongoing engagement can CHS hope to move beyond mere debunking or passive critique, actively shaping the dynamics of attention, imagination, and value that will define our technoscientific futures. This paper thus stands not as an endpoint, but as an open invitation – an initial map for a field that must constantly redraw its boundaries as new forms of hype arise. In the spirit of critical inquiry and generative skepticism, we look forward to further dialogue and the ongoing co-production of a CHS that is as dynamic, reflexive, and consequential as the phenomenon it seeks to understand.

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